

Providing access to cost-efficient, replicable,
safe and flexible CCUS

CCUS educational materials

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Coordinated by: SINTEF Energi AS - www.sintef.no/energy

About ACCSESS

If CO₂ capture and storage (CCS) is to become a relevant, large-scale technology for cutting carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, several barriers need to be addressed, and its deployment must be accelerated.

ACCSESS works to address key challenges to the successful implementation of CCS across Europe: namely, challenges related to CO₂ capture, CCS chains, and societal acceptance. The project focuses on four industrial sectors with the potential to drastically reduce CO₂ emissions by implementing CCS: waste-to-energy, pulp and paper, cement, and biorefineries.

ACCSESS started in May 2021. Its consortium consists of 18 partners from eight different European countries.

www.projectaccess.eu

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Abstract
<p>This report contains an assembly of educational materials that has been produced as part of the ACCESS project Task 12.2 on Citizen engagement and acceptance of CCUS. Information/education materials for citizens, cities, other stakeholders as well as ACCESS partners have been produced. The educational material consists of two videos on CO₂ capture from cement and pulp/paper respectively, three pamphlets and a power point slide pack (What is CCS and CDR?). The material has been produced with expertise in the consortium.</p> <p>There is also continuous communication throughout the ACCESS project through the website, blog posts and Linked In.</p>

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Refer to the ACCESS community in Zenodo.org for citation with DOI (<https://zenodo.org/communities/access>)

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Document Purpose

This document represents the deliverable “D12.4 CCUS Educational materials” of the ACCESS project. The material educational produced will serve to prepare information/education materials for citizens, cities and other stakeholders as well as ACCESS partners, with the objective to increase awareness and transmit important about CCS and CDR technologies. The material is based on the expertise in the consortium and validated with public and opinion leaders.

1.2 List of Acronyms and abbreviations

CCS	Carbon Capture and Storage or CO ₂ Capture and Storage
CDR	Carbon Dioxide Removal
CHAL	Chalmers Tekniska Hoegskola AB (Chalmers University of Technology)
SE	Stora Enso AB
SER	SINTEF Energy Research

1.3 Relation to other deliverables

This deliverable aims to contribute to workshops and other outreach activities that will contributing to shaping D12.11 – How sustainable cities can drive carbon dioxide removal – a handbook.

2 EDUCATIONAL MATERIAL

Task 12.2 in ACCESS aims to engage and inform stakeholders about CCUS, its societal benefits at large, and the marginal additional cost of the products produced with CCUS. The aim is to create an understanding and acceptance among cities and citizens of the solutions that CCUS can contribute to the development of the low-carbon society that is necessary to combat global warming. For CCUS to be successful and contribute to curbing CO₂ emissions at scale, it needs to become an integrated and obvious part of society and its infrastructure. In this context, a main hypothesis in ACCESS is that cities striving for sustainable urban development can become drivers for CCUS implementation. Bringing complementarity to this city-oriented approach, this part of ACCESS will also synthesize the project results as packages to foster CCUS technology and business model replicability.

Working towards this the ACCESS project aims to produce scientifically correct educational material, for fact-based learning on CCUS. The ACCESS project wishes to contribute to accelerating learning within and beyond the project, drawing on the experience from CCUS pioneers in the consortium through cross-sectorial approach; and transforming the narrative of CCUS through social innovation and creating a drive for high-value, low-carbon footprint products brought by CCUS.

The educational material produced to date and included in this deliverable:

- Educational Video on how to decarbonize cement production
- Educational video on Carbon Dioxide removal through CCS in pulp and paper
- Pamphlets based on the two videos
- A slide pack (“What is CCS and CDR?”)
- The ACCESS Website
- Blogs and new articles

The educational material is made available on the ACCESS web page and promoted in social media. It is distributed to partners in the project, who are encouraged to use material in their dissemination efforts during conferences and meetings where ACCESS and or CCUS as a topic is represented.

2.1 Video on cement production with CCS

SER has with support from VDZ and Fraunhofer and in coordination with the ACCESS project management team produced a script for a scientifically correct educational video on capture and storage of CO₂ from cement production, outlining why it needs to happen, and why capturing is necessary for cement production. The contents is based on the information on public concerns gathered in task 12.2.1 and the insights on societal impact of pioneering CCUS chains obtained in task 9.3.3. The script has been reviewed by other partners, in particular VDZ.

The video is produced by SER and is publicly available on YouTube and is presented on the ACCESS web page with an article descriptive of the contents of the video.

[How can we decarbonise cement production? - YouTube](#)

[How can we decarbonise cement production? – Access \(projectaccess.eu\)](#)

Figure 1. Screen captures from the educational video on CCS and cement production

2.2 Video on Pulp and Paper production with CCS

SER with support from CHAL and Stora Enso have in coordination with the ACCESS project management team produced a script for a scientifically correct educational video on capture and storage of CO₂ from pulp and paper production, outlining the potential for removing atmospheric CO₂ from waste biomass that is used for energy purposes in pulp and paper mills, the connection to with sustainable forest management.

The video is produced by SER and is publicly available on YouTube and is presented on the ACCESS web page with an article descriptive of the contents of the video.

Film on YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0wurHem9jMk>

ACCESS Website: <https://www.projectaccess.eu/2024/04/24/are-plants-the-key-to-succeeding-with-carbon-dioxide-removal-cdr/>

Figure 2. Screen captures from the educational video on CCS and pulp and paper.

2.3 Pamphlets

Based in the scripts for the two videos, pamphlets were produced with info on how to decarbonize cement production. The pamphlets have been uploaded to Zenodo.org in the ACCSESS community. The consortium members have access to the pamphlets in Word, for easy translation to other languages. The pamphlets are included in Annex A.

Additionally, a graphically more appealing pamphlet “What is CCS” has been produced, with a case study on CO₂ capture from cement, but also informing about that CO₂ has been stored under the North Sea since 1996.

2.4 Power point – What is CCS and CDR?

A slide pack “What is Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) and Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR)?” has been developed, with the aim of explaining CCS and CDR to non-experts in the field. The slide pack is published in PDF format on the ACCSESS website. The file is also available for the consortium in ppt format to facilitate translation into other languages. The power point includes a slide with links to recognized and trusted sites where further information about CCS and CCUS can be found. The slides are included in Annex B

2.5 Blogs, News Articles and the ACCSESS website

In addition to the educational material included in this deliverable, ACCSESS also has published blogs on its website and will continue to do so during the project lifetime. Blogs can typically be derived from scientific publications, with the aim of explaining and translate scientific results to a broader audience.

A PAMPHLETS

What is CCS?

Too much CO₂ in our atmosphere is the main driver of climate change. In 2015, the UN set a goal of limiting the increase in global temperatures to well below 1.5°C, compared to pre-industrial temperatures.

Carbon capture and storage (CCS) technologies capture CO₂ from industrial processes and store it permanently deep underground so it can't escape into the atmosphere.

In many industries, it would be better to avoid producing CO₂ altogether. However, for some industries, it is almost impossible to avoid CO₂ emissions.

CCS is crucial to meeting our climate targets, as it enables us to quickly reduce our CO₂ emissions from industries that are difficult to decarbonise but that our society depends on.

Case study: cement

Concrete is the second most used substance in the world. One of the main components of concrete is cement, and cement production alone is responsible for around 7% of global, man-made CO₂ emissions.

Concrete is difficult to replace. Even if we drastically increased our use of alternative construction materials, such as wood, there would still be a great need for concrete in buildings and infrastructure.

Therefore, we need to find a way to reduce our CO₂ emissions from cement production - and quickly.

Two thirds of CO₂ produced from making cement are released during the calcination of cement's key ingredient: limestone, and cannot be avoided.

Therefore, the only way to decarbonise cement production is to capture the CO₂ emissions and store them.

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It is important to remember that CCS is not *the* solution, but *one of many* solutions needed to create a sustainable future.

In Norway, CO₂ has been captured from natural gas at the Sleipner field and safely injected into the ground under the North Sea since 1996.

A lot of work has been done since then to make this technology better, more cost effective, and capable of being implemented at a large scale.

This project received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022487.

*CO₂ capture absorber unit being installed at the Heidelberg Materials cement kiln in Brevik, Norway, in 2023.
CO₂ capture operation planned from 2025.*

How can we decarbonise cement production?

Concrete is the second most used substance in the world, after water. Concrete is used in a lot of structures, from towering skyscrapers to bungalows, bridges and pavements.

One of the main components of concrete is cement, and cement production alone is responsible for around 7% of global, man-made CO₂ emissions. Too much CO₂ in our atmosphere is the main driver of climate change.

Cement is necessary for making concrete. We could use wood as a construction material instead, but even if we drastically increased our use of wood, there would still be a great need for concrete in buildings and infrastructure, particularly as urbanisation is increasing around the world. Therefore, we need a way to reduce our CO₂ emissions from cement – and quickly.

Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) means capturing CO₂ from industrial processes and storing it deep underground where it can't escape back into the atmosphere. Since 1996, CO₂ separated from natural gas at the Sleipner field has been captured and safely injected into the ground under the North Sea. A lot of work has been done since then to make this technology better, most cost effective, and capable of being implemented at a large scale.

In many industries, it would be better to avoid producing CO₂ altogether. However, two thirds of the CO₂ produced from making cement are released during the calcination of the key ingredient: limestone, and cannot be avoided. Therefore, the only way to decarbonise cement production is to capture and store the CO₂.

In 2015, the UN set a goal of limiting the increase in global temperatures to well below 1.5°C, compared to pre-industrial temperatures. CCS is crucial for meeting this target, as it enables us to reduce CO₂ emissions from industries like cement, which society depends on but are difficult to decarbonise. However, it is important to remember that CCS is not *the* solution, but *one of many* solutions needed to create a sustainable future.

Industrial-scale removal of CO₂ from the atmosphere: CCS from pulp and paper production

Carbon capture and storage (CCS) technologies are used to capture CO₂ emissions from industrial processes and store them safely and permanently underground, instead of releasing them into the atmosphere. However, plants capture and store CO₂ naturally – and have done for millennia.

Trees, like many other plants, need CO₂, water and sunlight in order to grow. This process is known as photosynthesis. The carbon from the absorbed CO₂ stays in the trees, and any products made from trees, for their entire lifetime. When the wood finally decays or is burned, the CO₂ is released back into the atmosphere – unless we capture and store it.

CCS on processes that use fossil resources can prevent additional CO₂ emissions. But CCS on processes that use biomass – like trees – will actually remove CO₂ from the atmosphere. This process of removing atmospheric CO₂ is known as “negative emissions” or “Carbon Dioxide Removal” (CDR), when more CO₂ is taken out of the atmosphere than is put into it.

One industry with significant potential for CDR is pulp and paper. Pulp mills use woody biomass, to produce a wide range of products, from cardboard and other packaging materials to napkins and nappy fluff. After most of the biomass has been used to create the product, the leftover biomass is used as fuel to generate heat and electricity for the production process in the mill. When this fuel is burned, the carbon contained in the biomass is released as CO₂, which we can then capture and permanently store.

But this is just one piece of the puzzle. While biomass is a renewable resource, we must remember that its potential for CDR is limited. We will still need to drastically cut fossil CO₂ emissions in order to meet climate goals. In addition, forests play a crucial role in maintaining the health of our planet and protecting biodiversity. Therefore, we must also protect and cultivate our forests through practices such as sustainable forest management, reforestation and afforestation.

These measures together can be part of a future that both contributes to CDR and supports the health of the Earth’s natural lungs.

B POWER POINT – WHAT IS CCS AND CDR?

What is Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) and Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR)?

Photo: Hafslund Oslo Celsio, Einar Aslaksen

CO₂ as a driver for climate change

- Increasing CO₂ concentrations in the atmosphere from human activities is the main driver of climate change
- CO₂ absorbs infrared radiation and reflects it back to earth → greenhouse effect
- Concentration of CO₂ reached around 425 ppm in 2024

Picture: [The Keeling Curve \(ucsd.edu\)](https://www.ucsd.edu/~keeling/)

CO₂ and global warming trends

- Global warming leads to extreme weather events and rising sea levels
- Reduction of CO₂ emissions is crucial to curb climate change
- Paris Agreement: limit the temperature increase to 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels
- EU, USA and many countries worldwide aim to reach carbon neutrality by 2050

Graph creator: [Ed Hawkins](#) Licensor: [University of Reading, UK](#), CC BY 4.0

CCS – part of the EU climate toolbox

Solar photovoltaic and solar thermal

Heat pumps and geothermal energy

Electrolysers and fuel cells

Onshore wind and offshore renewables

Sustainable biogas / biomethane

Batteries and storage

Grid technologies

Carbon capture and storage

CCS is a key to reaching climate goals

- CCS reduces CO₂ emissions from fossil power generation and industrial activities
- CCS only alternative where CO₂ emissions are part of the process (e.g. cement)
- Removal of CO₂ from the atmosphere is possible through Bio-CCS and DACCS

Source: [United Nations](#)

CCS in 3 steps

1. Capture CO₂ at the industrial point sources (or from air/ocean/biomass)
2. Transport CO₂ by pipeline, ship, train or on the road to a storage site
3. Inject CO₂ in the underground

CO₂ capture processes (1): Absorption

- CO₂ is «washed» from a gas mixture with a dedicated liquid
- Energy is required to remove CO₂ from the liquid
 - Typically mainly heat, some electricity
- The liquid is circulated and re-used

Heidelberg Materials,
Brevik

Picture: Heidelberg Materials

Hafslund Celsio Oslo,
Klemetsrud

Picture: Hafslund Oslo Celsio, Einar Aslaksen

CO₂ capture processes (2): Adsorption

- CO₂ sticks to particles
- Energy must be supplied to release the CO₂ from the particles
 - Pressure Swing (mostly electricity)
 - Temperature Swing (mostly heat)
- It is a periodic batch process
- The particles are re-used

CO₂ capture processes (3): Membranes

- CO₂ is «filtered» through a thin membrane
- The membrane is designed to allow more CO₂ to pass through than other gases
- A pressure difference is needed across the membrane
 - Electricity is needed

Transport of CO₂

- CO₂ must be compressed before the transport
- CO₂ is transported efficiently via pipelines, particularly for large distances and volumes of CO₂
- Liquid CO₂ for transportation in ships, tanks or containers

Transportation – chains and clusters

CO₂ capture & conditioning

Intermediate storage & loading

Unloading, intermediate storage, re-conditioning, injection

Storage of CO₂

= Injecting CO₂ into geological formations

- Need of suitable geological formation
- Compression of CO₂ and injection using wells
- Caprock acts as a natural seal through capillary forces to prevent CO₂ slip
- Use of technologies like seismic imaging for monitoring
- CO₂ has been safely stored offshore Norway since 1996 (Sleipner)

CDR, Bio-CCS & DACCS

- Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR) as a complementary tool to emission reduction and allows to compensate for technically too challenging or too costly to abate emissions
- Possible through nature-based and technological solutions
- Reforestation: nature-based Carbon Dioxide Removal
- Bio-CCS: Carbon Dioxide Removal via photosynthesis and CCS technology
- Direct Air CO₂ Capture and Storage (DACCS) removes CO₂ directly from the air

Industrial sectors in ACCESS with potential for Bio-CCS

- Pulp and paper
- Waste-to-energy
- Cement, when using biogenic fuels
- Biorefineries

Mineralisation of CO₂ for permanent storage

- CO₂ can react with dissolved alkalinity of rock to form stable carbonates
- This process traps the CO₂ in solid form
- Carbonates formed through mineralisation are stable over geological timescales and ensure long-term storage of CO₂

Capture: CO₂ is captured from industrial emissions or directly from the atmosphere

Reaction: The captured CO₂ reacts with minerals, e.g. olivine, serpentine, basalt or industrial residues

Product: The reaction produces stable carbonate minerals (e.g., calcite, magnesite) that are solid and can be stored or used as a resource

For further information

- [ACCSESS](#)
- [Global CCS Institute](#)
- [International Energy Agency \(IEA\)](#)
- [Zero Emissions Platform \(ZEP\)](#)
- [Norwegian CCS Research Centre \(NCCS\)](#)
- [SINTEFblog CCS](#)

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The logo for ACCESS features a circular icon on the left, divided into three colored segments: blue at the top, orange at the bottom-left, and teal at the bottom-right. To the right of the icon, the word "ACCESS" is written in a bold, sans-serif font. The letters are colored as follows: 'A' is white, the first 'C' is blue, the second 'C' is teal, 'S' is orange, and 'E', 'S', and 'S' are white.

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